

D7.10 – Final monitoring and evaluation report

WP7 – Management and Coordination

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Mid-term Monitoring & Evaluation report

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1. INTRODUCTION

The gEneSys Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) strategy, thoroughly described in D7.3, elucidated modes and timeframe for the evaluation of the project. The project's M&E pursued the following objectives:

1. Making sure project's deliverable and outputs were delivered as planned, and that the stated objectives and deadlines of the project were met.
2. Ensuring the tasks ran smoothly and in the full respect of the project's founding principles of transparency, mutual learning, collaboration and valorization of the competencies of all the participants (including senior and junior staff) as declared and agreed among partner organizations during the kickoff meeting (see D 7.1.).
3. Capturing emerging phenomena and requests in the wider environment and within the consortium that may warrant a shift in the specific tasks and/or objectives.

The current final M&E deliverable describes the results of four rounds of evaluation carried out during the project. The deliverable is structured as follows: first we recap the M&E's dimensions and indicators and the modes and timeline for verification. Then we present the results of the evaluation activities.

2. MONITORING AND EVALUATION STRATEGY

2.1 Dimensions and indicators

Based on the above-mentioned objectives, the following M&E dimensions were identified:

EVALUATION DIMENSION 1. *Internal Relationships' Management*

This dimension is intended to gather insights into the functioning of the gEneSys consortium and anticipate and resolve potential bottlenecks induced by conflicts and divergent interests and working practices among partners that may hinder the achievement of the project's objectives. Overall, this M&E dimension seeks to respond to the following evaluation questions:

- (1) How well do participants collaborate by sharing knowledge, information and resources?
- (2) How well is the consortium able to adapt its organisational practices to the changeable circumstances and demands coming from the inside and outside of the network?
- (3) To what extent are participants able to manage conflicts and tensions while remaining respectful of the divergent working practices and organisational

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priorities?

(4) How well is the coordinating structure able to manage diversity and heterogeneity within the network?

(5) How well can the participants manage the individual and shared resources made available by the network (i.e. time, lessons, money, staff)?

(6) To what extent does the project foster EU integration and international cooperation?

(7) To what extent have early career researchers been involved in the project activities?

EVALUATION DIMENSION 2. Internal – Project activities and outputs

This evaluation dimension gathers information about the extent to which the project objectives are achieved through the delivery of the project's outcomes and outputs and about the perceptions of partners regarding the project's implementation. It also takes into consideration the added value of the projects' outputs for the stakeholders and the society at large. Overall, this evaluation dimension seeks to respond to the following questions:

1. Were the project's outputs delivered on time?
2. Did the project's activities and outputs fulfill the objectives set for the project?
3. Did the project's outputs add new elements to the existing scientific knowledge and policy debate?
4. To what extent are the partners and the whole consortium able to translate scientific and technical information into knowledge understandable by policymakers and society at large?
5. To what extent have the project's key themes (e.g. just transition, gendered impacts of energy transition etc.) been mainstreamed into the research of the partner organisations, beyond the gEneSys project?
6. To what extent are the resources provided for the project (e.g. budget, time, guidance) perceived as sufficient by partner organisations?

EVALUATION DIMENSION 3 – External – stakeholder engagement

This third evaluation dimension explores the extent to which the consortium engages with relevant stakeholders and builds relationships that may help in disseminating project's results.

1. To what extent do partner organisations create new ties with external stakeholders?
2. To what extent are the project's activities and outputs perceived as relevant by the external stakeholders?
3. To what extent are the project's results disseminated among the external

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stakeholders?

4. To what extent are the project's results disseminated among the external stakeholders?

5. To what extent are the stakeholders committed to or aligned with sustainable practices and long- term project's objectives?

Given these dimensions, we established a set of indicators to evaluate each of them. These are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of the project's deliverable and associated information.

Dimension	Questions	Indicators	Means of evaluation
1. Internal Relationships' Management	How well partners collaborate by sharing knowledge, information and resources	1.a Perception of bottlenecks in the sharing of information and resources within the consortium	Surveys to all the participants
	How well is the consortium able to adapt its organisational practices to the changeable circumstances and demands coming from the inside and outside of the network	1.b Perception of responsiveness and adaptability to internal changes	Surveys to all the participants
		1.c Perception of responsiveness and adaptability to external changes and demands	
	To what extent are participants able to manage conflicts and tensions	1.d Frequency to which different working practices created bottlenecks in the project's activities	Surveys to all the participants
	How well is the coordinating structure able to manage diversity and heterogeneity within the network	1.e Perceived ability of the coordinating organization to manage internal relationships	Surveys to all the participants
	How well can the participants manage the individual and shared resources made available by the network (i.e. time, lessons, money, staff)?	1.f Perceived ability to make use of the resources made available within the network	Surveys to all the participants
	To what extent do partners perceive to get benefits from being part of the consortium	1.g Perceived benefits deriving from being part of the consortium	Surveys to all the participants
	To what extent does the project foster EU integration and international	1.h Increase of the perceived benefits coming from pan-European cooperation	Surveys to all the participants

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	cooperation?	1.i Perceived collaboration/power hierarchies between partners from different European regions	
		1.l Perceived integration of non EU-partner in the project's activities	
	To what extent have early career researchers been involved in the project activities?	1.m. Number of early career researchers working on project activities	Survey to team leaders
		1.n. Number of deliverables where an early career research appear as author	Review of deliverables
	1.o Number of training/networking opportunities for early career researchers	Survey to team leaders	
Internal – Project activities and outputs.	Were the project's outputs and tasks delivered on time	2.a Number of deliverables submitted as planned	Review of deliverables and tasks
	Did the project's activities and outputs fulfill the objectives set for the project?	2.b Number and type of project's objectives fulfilled by each output	Review of the outputs produced by the project Surveys to advisory board members
	Did the project's outputs add new elements to the existing scientific knowledge and policy debate?	2.c Perceived added value	Survey to advisory board members
		2.d Number of scientific publications produced	Review of the scientific publications produced
	To what extent is the project consortium able to translate scientific and technical knowledge into information that can be understood and used by policymakers and by the society at large?	2.e Number of policy briefs and policy documents produced	Review of outputs
		2.f Number of materials produced for public outreach	Review of outputs
	To what extent have the project's key themes (e.g. just transition, gendered impacts of energy transition etc.) been mainstreamed into the research of the partner organisations, beyond the genesys	2.g Perceived integration of key themes into other research streams	Survey to team leaders

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	project?		
	To what extent are the resources provided for the project (e.g. budget, time, guidance) perceived as sufficient by partner organisations?	2.h Perceived efficiency of the project	Survey to team leaders
3.External – stakeholder engagement	To what extent do partner organisations create new ties with external stakeholders?	3a Number and type of new connections created outside the consortium	Survey to team leaders
	To what extent are the project's activities and outputs perceived as relevant by the external stakeholders?	3b Perceived relevance by external stakeholders	Survey to external stakeholders
	To what extent are the project's results disseminated among the external stakeholders?	3c Number of dissemination activities performed	Survey to team leaders
	To what extent are the stakeholders committed to or aligned with sustainable practices and long-term project's objectives?	3d Number of meetings, workshops, or conferences attended during the project and at the end.	Excel form to send to all the partners.
		3e Monitor the extent and tone of media coverage related to the project through social media.	Excel form to send to all the external stakeholders.

2.1 Evaluation modes and timeline

The gEneSys M&E strategy has envisaged three different instruments for the collection of evaluation data:

- 1) **An excel sheet used to track tasks and deliverables** and monitor whether were performed as per proposal (indicator #2a) and which project's objectives they fulfill (indicator # 2b). In addition, the excel sheet is also used to track the number of scientific publications (indicator 2d) and of documents for policymakers and the public produced during the project (indicator 2e and 2f).

DELIVERABLE NAME	TASK LEADER	DATE OF PLANNED SUBMISSION AS FOR PROPOSAL	SUBMITTED AS FOR TIMELINE? INSERT YES/NO AND DATE OF SUBMISSION	OBJECTIVE FULFILLED	DOES an early career research appear as author

- 2) **An online survey to collect input from partner organizations. This survey has** been created through the CNR's Limesurvey account and includes questions for all the participants as well as for team leaders. This survey contains questions regarding working modes, information sharing, the staff working within each team, the type of new ties created by the research group and the research streams beyond the gEneSys project. The survey can be found in Appendix 1 of this document.

3. M&E RESULTS

3.1 Survey results

In this section, we comparatively present the results of the four rounds of the M&E survey conducted in October 2023, June 2024, April 2025, and March 2026.

Figure 1: Results of the question “Since the project’s onset, how frequently did you experience bottlenecks in the sharing of information and resources within the consortium?”

Figure 1 presents the perceived bottlenecks in the sharing of information and resources within the consortium across the four monitoring periods. In the first M&E round, most of respondents reported not experiencing any bottlenecks, although a substantial number (7) indicated that they sometimes encountered such issues. In the second round, this pattern initially appeared to improve, with an increase in the number of partners reporting no bottlenecks (9) and a reduction in those experiencing them occasionally (4). However, this phase also marked the emergence of a more critical perception, as one partner reported experiencing bottlenecks very frequently, indicating that while overall perceptions improved, some more severe issues persisted at the individual level.

From the third round onwards, the distribution stabilized into a more balanced pattern. In the third M&E period, responses were evenly split between partners reporting no bottlenecks and those reporting occasional bottlenecks (5), with no cases of frequent or very frequent issues. This suggests a partial convergence of experiences across partners, with fewer extreme positions. In the fourth and final round, this balanced pattern largely persisted, although with a slight shift towards more frequent acknowledgment of bottlenecks: the number of partners reporting no issues remained stable (5), while those reporting occasional bottlenecks increased slightly (6). No respondents reported frequent or very frequent bottlenecks in this phase.

Overall, the results indicate an initial improvement between the first and second periods, followed by a stabilization in the later stages of the project, where

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bottlenecks were still present but generally limited to occasional occurrences rather than systemic or severe constraints.

Figure 2: Results of the question “Since the project’s onset, how frequently did you perceive that different working practices have created bottlenecks in the delivery of the project’s activities?”

Figure 2 illustrates the extent to which divergent working practices are perceived as a source of bottlenecks in the delivery of project activities across the four monitoring periods. In the first M&E round, responses were relatively balanced, with a slight predominance of partners indicating that such differences sometimes created bottlenecks (8), compared to those who did not perceive any issue (7). In the second round, the situation appeared to improve. The number of respondents reporting no bottlenecks increased to 8, while those indicating occasional difficulties decreased to 5. However, this phase also saw the emergence of a limited number of more critical perceptions, with one partner reporting that divergent working practices frequently created bottlenecks.

In the third round, the distribution shifted again, suggesting a partial re-emergence of coordination challenges. The number of partners reporting no bottlenecks decreased to 4, while those indicating occasional bottlenecks increased to 6. No respondents reported frequent or very frequent issues in this phase, indicating that while coordination frictions became more widespread, they remained of moderate intensity. In the fourth and final round, this trend consolidated further. The number of partners reporting no bottlenecks decreased to 3, while those reporting occasional bottlenecks increased to 7. Additionally, one respondent again indicated that such issues were experienced frequently. As in previous rounds, no respondents reported very frequent bottlenecks.

In general terms, the results suggest an initial improvement between the first and second periods, followed by a gradual increase in the perception of coordination challenges related to differing working practices. However, these challenges remained largely confined to occasional occurrences, with only isolated cases of more frequent difficulties, indicating that while alignment across partners required ongoing attention, it did not evolve into a systemic or critical issue.

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Figure 3: Results of question “Do you think that the project coordination team (CNR) has been able so far to manage well the relationships among partners (CNR team should skip this question)?”

Figure 3 shows partners' assessments of CNR's role in managing relations within the consortium across the four monitoring periods. Positive evaluations decreased over the time, from 11 respondents in the first round to 9 in the second and stabilized at 5 in both the third and fourth rounds. At the same time, more differentiated views emerged: “not always” responses increased (from 0 to 4 and then 3), a small number of “no” responses appeared in the final round (1), and non-applicable responses declined compared to earlier phases. Overall, while perceptions remain generally positive, the results indicate a gradual shift towards more nuanced and less uniformly favorable assessments in the later stages of the project.

Figure 4: Results of the question: “Since the project’s onset, did you perceive to be able to take full advantage from the resources made available by the consortium (e.g. funds to attend conferences, opportunities to expand professional networks)?”

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Figure 4 shows partners' perceptions of the utilization of project resources across the four monitoring periods. Overall, responses remained largely positive throughout the project. In the first round, most respondents reported full utilization (11), with a small number indicating limitations. In the second round, positive responses remained high (10), but a slight increase in perceived constraints emerged (3 “not always” and 1 “no”). In the third round, positive evaluations decreased (8), while some limitations persisted (2 “not always”). In the fourth round, perceptions improved again (9 “yes”), with a stable number of “not always” responses (2) and no “no” responses. The findings seem to suggest generally effective use of resources, with some temporary fluctuations in perceived limitations over time.

Figure 5: Results of question: “For EU partners only: Since the project’s onset, how often did you perceive the benefits coming from pan-European collaboration?”

Figure 5 presents partners' perceptions of the benefits derived from pan-European collaboration across the four monitoring periods. Overall, responses remain positive, although with some fluctuation over time. In the first round, benefits were mainly perceived as occurring “very frequently” (5) or “sometimes” (4), with a smaller number indicating “frequently” (3) and “not at all” (2). In the second round, perceptions shifted towards higher intensity, with a peak in “frequently” responses (7), while “very frequently” declined (2) and no respondents selected “not at all”. In the third and fourth rounds, responses became more evenly distributed across categories, with a slight decline in more positive responses and the reappearance of lower-frequency categories. Overall, while the perceived benefits of pan-European collaboration remain clearly positive, the results suggest a gradual stabilization towards more moderate and differentiated evaluations over time.

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Figure 6: Results of question “Since the project’s onset, how often did you perceive that power hierarchies between European regions or with countries outside Europe have influenced the way in which project’s activities have been carried out?”

Figure 6 explores whether power hierarchies between European regions or with non-European countries are perceived as constraints. Overall, such issues are largely not perceived as problematic across all monitoring periods. In the first round, responses were evenly split between “not at all” (6) and “sometimes” (6), with only one respondent indicating “frequently”. In the second round, perceptions improved, with most respondents selecting “not at all” (8) and fewer indicating occasional issues (3). This pattern remains stable in the later stages. In the third and fourth rounds, the majority of respondents continued to report no perceived constraints (7 in both rounds), with a limited number indicating “sometimes” (2 and 3, respectively) and no reports of frequent or very frequent issues. Overall, the findings suggest that power hierarchies are not considered a significant constraint within the project, with perceptions becoming slightly more positive over time.

Figure 7: Results of question “For non-EU partners only (e.g., UK and Africa): Since the project’s onset, how often did you perceive that your inputs were not adequately incorporated or valued because of your geographical location?”

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Figure 7 examines whether non-EU partners perceived that their inputs were not adequately incorporated or valued due to their geographical location. Across all monitoring periods, most responses are non-applicable, reflecting the limited number of respondents concerned. Among those who did respond, perceptions are generally positive. In the first and third rounds, only one respondent indicated that this issue was not experienced at all. In the second round, three respondents reported no such perception, while one indicated that this occurred frequently. In the fourth round, the number of “not at all” responses increased to four, with no reports of occasional or frequent issues.

Figure 8: Results of question “For team leaders only: how many early career researchers work on the project’s activities in your team (early career researchers should have no more than three years postdoctoral experience)?”

Figure 8 reports the number of early career researchers involved in project activities, based on responses from team leaders. Among respondents, the presence of early career researchers varies moderately over time. In the first round, most team leaders reported either no early career researchers (3) or one to two (2), with only one indicating three or more. In the second round, responses shifted slightly towards greater involvement, with an increase in teams reporting one to two early career researchers (4) and no cases of three or more. In the third and fourth rounds, the distribution steadied, with a small number of teams reporting no early career researchers (2 and 1, respectively) and a similar number indicating one to two (2 in both rounds), while no teams reported higher involvement. In general terms, the results suggest a limited but relatively stable inclusion of early career researchers in project activities over time.

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Figure 9: Results of question “For early career researchers only: Since the project’s outputs, how frequently did you perceive that being part of the gEneSys project has offered you training/networking opportunities?”

Figure 9 presents early career researchers' perceptions of the training and networking opportunities provided by the gEneSys project. Overall, responses indicate a generally positive perception. In the first and second rounds, opportunities were mainly perceived as frequent (2 in both rounds), with some indications of “sometimes” (2 in the first round) and “very frequently” (1 in the second round). In the third and fourth rounds, responses became slightly more diversified, with a small number of “not at all” and “sometimes” responses appearing, while “frequently” remained stable (2 in both rounds). The results suggest that gEneSys has consistently provided training and networking opportunities to early career researchers, with perceptions remaining positive over time despite some variability.

Figure 10: Results of question “For team leaders only: Since the project’s onset, how frequently did you perceive that the resources provided for the project (e.g., budget, time, guidance) were sufficient to effectively deliver the assigned activities?”

Figure 10 presents team leaders' perceptions of whether project resources (e.g.

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budget, time, guidance) were sufficient to effectively deliver activities. Responses indicate a generally positive but slightly declining perception over time. In the first and second rounds, resources were mainly perceived as frequently or very frequently sufficient (2–2 in both categories), with a small number of “sometimes” responses. In the third round, perceptions shifted towards more moderate evaluations, with an increase in “frequently” responses (3) but a decrease in “very frequently” (1). In the fourth round, more critical views emerged, with “sometimes” becoming the most common response (3) and a small number of “not at all” responses appearing (1), while positive responses declined. While resources are still generally perceived as adequate, the results suggest a gradual shift towards more cautious and less consistently positive assessments in the later stages of the project.

Figure 11: Results of question “For team leaders only: Since the project’s onset, how frequently did you perceive that your team has taken advantage of the gEneSys project to create ties with external stakeholders?”

Figure 11 shows team leaders' perceptions of how frequently their teams have used the project to establish relationships with external stakeholders. Responses indicate a positive but gradually moderating pattern over time. In the first round, stakeholder engagement was mainly perceived as frequent or very frequent (2 and 3 responses, respectively). In the second round, “frequently” responses increased slightly (3), while “very frequently” declined (1) and some “sometimes” responses emerged (2). In the third and fourth rounds, the pattern shifted further towards moderate frequencies, with “frequently” becoming the most common response (2 and 4, respectively) and “very frequently” disappearing.

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Figure 12: For team leaders only: Since the project’s onset, how many opportunities to disseminate project’s activities and/or outputs to external stakeholders did you have (e.g., presentation in conferences, running workshops/trainings)?

Figure 12 reports on the number of dissemination opportunities (e.g. conferences, workshops, training) experienced by team leaders. Responses indicate a consistent level of engagement in dissemination activities across the project, although with some variation over time. In the first and second rounds, most respondents reported participating in one to two events (3 and 4, respectively), with a smaller number indicating three or more opportunities (3 and 2). In the third and fourth rounds, the distribution shifted slightly towards higher engagement, with stable or increasing reports of three or more events (2 and 4, respectively), while one to two events remained common (2 and 1). The results suggest a steady involvement in dissemination activities, with a tendency towards increased intensity in the later stages of the project.

Figure 13: Results of question “Do you think that the gEneSys consortium is able to respond well to the changing circumstances within the consortium (e.g., new people added)?”

Lastly, Figure 13 presents respondents' assessments of the consortium's ability to

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respond to changing circumstances (e.g. onboarding new members). Across all monitoring periods, evaluations are overwhelmingly positive.

In the first and second rounds, all respondents indicated that the consortium responded well to changes (15 and 14 “yes”, respectively). In the third round, positive responses remained dominant (9), with only one non-applicable response. In the fourth round, positive evaluations continued to prevail (8), although a small number of respondents indicated that this was not always the case (3). The results suggest a consistently strong capacity of the consortium to adapt to changing circumstances, with only minor signs of more nuanced assessments in the final phase.

3.2 Review of project deliverables

Other dimensions of the project, especially those related to the timely delivery of the project's outputs, were monitored by the coordination team through an excel sheet. In particular, the team assessed whether the deliverables were submitted on time and which project's objectives they fulfilled.

The project's objectives are the following:

OBJECTIVE 1. Building the evidence base on structural and cultural forms of discrimination that act as barriers to women's full participation in energy systems (as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, decision makers, citizens and consumers).

OBJECTIVE 2. Identifying who are the power holders, the change actors and the stakeholders who influence the 'greening' agenda through policy/political, technology, environmental, social, and economic instruments, and interventions.

OBJECTIVE 3. Advancing scholarly understanding of how gender equality can be a lever and the outcome of transition to sustainable low-energy world.

OBJECTIVE 4. Advancing scholarly understanding of intersectional aspects of gender equality in 'green' policies, practices, and actions, including implementation of SDG7 targets.

OBJECTIVE 5. Increasing the participation and influence of women in energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, decision makers, consumers, and citizens.

OBJECTIVE 6. Promoting and facilitating international cooperation between Europe and Africa on dissemination of the evidence base on the importance of gender in energy transition with impact on the UN High level Dialogue on Energy and on implementation of SDGs.

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Table 2: Overview of the project's deliverable and associated information.

n.	Deliverable name	Task leader	Date of planned submission as for proposal	Submitted as for timeline? insert yes/no and date of submission	Objective fulfilled	Does early career researchers (no more than 3 years postdoctoral experience) appear as authors
D1.1	Systematic literature review of studies at the nexus of gender equality and sustainable energy systems and ontology of energy systems	CNR	30 Sep 2023	no 07/11/2023	OBJECTIVES 1 and 3	yes
D1.2	Report on Gendered assessment of the energy systems knowledge community and EU policies for sustainable energy systems(Leader : ENEA, M13)	ENEA	29 Feb 2024	no 04/03/2024	OBJECTIVES 1, 2 and 4	yes
D1.3	A multi-country, comparative, gendered assessment survey of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems.	CNR	30 Apr 2024	no 04/03/2025	OBJECTIVES 1, 2, 3 and 4	yes
D2.1	Report with analytical model	Fraunhofer	30 Nov 2023	no 08/10/2024	OBJECTIVES 3 and 4	yes
D2.2	Report on theoretical framework and survey results	Fraunhofer	28 Feb 2025	no 24/07/2025	OBJECTIVES 3 and 4	yes
D2.3	Theoretical framework report	Fraunhofer	31 Oct 2024	REMOVED	OBJECTIVES 3 and 4	
D2.4	Case study report	Fraunhofer	31 Mar 2025	no 24/07/2025	OBJECTIVES 3 and 4	yes

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D2.5	Final report	Fraunhofer	30 Sep 2025	no 26/02/2026	OBJECTIVES 3 and 4	yes
D3.1	Guidance notes for education policy makers on integrating gender perspective into all levels of education on transitions in energy system	UJ	31 Jul 2024	Yes	OBJECTIVE 1	yes
D3.2	Policy briefs on intersectional and gender-sensitive energy transformation	UJ	30 Nov 2025	no 29/12/2025	OBJECTIVE 1	no
D3.3	Analyses of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition	UJ	30 Nov 2025	no 17/12/2025	OBJECTIVE 5	yes
D3.4	Toolbox with good practices and new methods in teaching materials and curriculum	Fraunhofer	31 Dec 2025	Yes	OBJECTIVES 1 and 5	yes
D4.1	Report on past and current international cooperation initiatives between Europe and Africa	AIMS	31 Mar 2024	no 08/04/2024	OBJECTIVES 2 and 6	no
D4.2	Mechanisms and instruments for operationalising EU-Africa cooperation on implementing SDGs	AIMS	31 Mar 2026	PENDING	OBJECTIVE 6	
D4.3	Conceptualising and operationalising the values of equity, justice, fairness, and sustainability in African research and innovation	AIMS	28 Feb 2026	PENDING	OBJECTIVE 6	

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D5.1	Report on selected indicators for pathways model	IMPERIAL	31 Jul 2024	no 23/08/2024	OBJECTIVE 3	no
D5.2	D5.2 Report on gender perspective into energy SHIFTS	IMPERIAL	31 Jan 2024	no 01/02/2024	OBJECTIVE 3	no
D5.3	D5.3 Integrating gender perspectives into EUA recommendations for research, innovation, and education	IMPERIAL	31 Oct 2025	no 13/01/2026	OBJECTIVES 1 and 5	no
D5.4	D5.4 Analysis of co-created pathways and scenarios	IMPERIAL	31 Jan 2026	Yes	OBJECTIVES 1 and 5	no
D5.5	Gendering the targets of SDG7 for gender sensitive implementation efforts.	IMPERIAL	30 Apr 2026	PENDING	OBJECTIVES 1 and 5	
D6.1	Communication, Dissemination, and Impact strategy	PORTIA	31 Jul 2023	Yes	N/A	yes
D6.2	Review and update of Communication, Dissemination, and Impact strategy	PORTIA	31 Jul 2024	no 05/08/2024	N/A	yes
D6.3	Report on influential communities of actors and stakeholders in energy transition for SDGs	PORTIA	30 Jun 2025	no 24/07/2025	N/A	no
D6.4	Sustainability strategy and action report	PORTIA	30 Apr 2026	PENDING	N/A	
D6.5	Report on the gEneSys engagement with and impact on the	PORTIA	30 Apr 2026	PENDING	N/A	

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	wider energy transition landscape					
D7.1	Programme and summary/outline of the project status and decisions taken at the Kick-off meeting	CNR	31 Mar 2023	no 03/04/2023	N/A	yes
D7.2	Initial data management plan including Protection of Personal Data (POPD)	CNR	31 Jul 2023	no 04/09/2023	N/A	yes
D7.3	Monitoring and Evaluation strategy	CNR	31 Jul 2023	no 08/10/2024	N/A	no
D7.4	First financial report	CNR	30 Sep 2023	REMOVED	N/A	
D7.5	Second financial report	CNR	29 Feb 2024	REMOVED	N/A	
D7.6	Programme and summary/outline of the project advancements and decisions taken at the 2nd steering committee meeting	CNR	31 Mar 2024	Yes	N/A	yes
D7.7	Mid-term monitoring and evaluation report	CNR	31 Jul 2024	no 05/08/2024	N/A	no
D7.8	Programme and summary/outline of the project advancements and decisions taken at the 3rd steering committee meeting	CNR	31 Mar 2025	no 24/07/2025	N/A	no
D7.9	Final data management plan	CNR	31 Jul 2024	Yes	N/A	yes
D7.10	Final evaluation report	CNR	30 Apr 2026	PENDING	N/A	
D8.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	CNR	31 Jul 2023	no 01/08/2024	N/A	yes

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As shown in Table 2, most of the project's deliverables were submitted broadly in line with the planned timeline. A limited number of deliverables (e.g. D1.1, D5.1, D6.2, D7.7) were submitted with minor delays of a few days or weeks. More substantial delays affected some deliverables linked to data collection and analysis activities, mainly due to the timing of the approval process by the CNR Ethics Committee (see Technical Report for details). A number of deliverables are still pending, as expected given their scheduling in the final phase of the project.

Regarding the project's objectives, a large share of completed deliverables contributed to Objective 1 (building the evidence base on structural and cultural forms of discrimination in energy systems) and Objective 3 (advancing scholarly understanding of the role of gender equality in energy transitions). This reflects the strategic focus of the first phase of the project on knowledge production and analytical groundwork. Objective 5 is mainly addressed by activities scheduled in the second half of the project and is therefore more prominently reflected in later deliverables.

Finally, the involvement of early career researchers appears uneven across deliverables. While several outputs include early career researchers among the authors, their presence remains limited overall, suggesting the need for stronger integration of this group in future project activities and outputs.

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4. ANNEXES

4.1. ANNEX 1: questionnaire for partner organisations

Dear colleagues

This questionnaire is intended to monitor the progresses of the gEneSys consortium from a relational and operational standpoint. As such, it should be considered as an internal tool to capture emerging challenges within the consortium and try to resolve them before that they become detrimental to the project's activities or the project's collaborative climate. Therefore, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions as openly and sincerely as possible. The questionnaire is anonymous so it will not be possible to detect your identity. The participation is voluntary but please consider that your input is critical to improve the consortium's internal dynamics.

The questionnaire is composed of mostly closed-ended questions (please choose only one option per question). At the end of the questionnaire, you can add your free comments in

the text box. Should you have questions or doubts, you can contact Serena Tagliacozzo at this email address serena.taaliacozzo@irpps.cnr.it

Thank you in advance for your co-operation. Regards

The CNR coordination team

a. Since the project's onset, how frequently did you experience bottlenecks in the sharing of information and resources within the consortium?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3) Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

b. Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that different working practices have created bottlenecks in the delivery of the project's activities?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3) Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

c. Do you think that the gEneSys consortium is able to respond well to the changing circumstances within the consortium (e.g., new people added)?

- 1) yes
- 2) no
- 3) not always

d. Do you think that the gEneSys consortium is able to adapt well to the changing circumstances

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outside the consortium (e.g., new inputs from emergent research)?

- 1) yes
- 2) no
- 3) not always

e. Do you think that the project coordination team (CNR) has been able so far to manage well the relationships among partners (**CNR team should skip this question**)?

- 1) yes
- 2) no
- 3) not always

f. Since the project's onset, did you perceive to be able to take full advantage from the resources made available by the consortium (e.g. funds to attend conferences, opportunities to expand professional networks)?

- 1) yes
- 2) no
- 3) not always

g. **For EU partners only:** Since the project's onset, how often did you perceive the benefits coming from pan-European collaboration

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3) Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

h. Since the project's onset, how often did you perceive that power hierarchies between European regions or with countries outside Europe have influenced the way in which project's activities have been carried out?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3) Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

i. **For non-EU partners only (e.g., UK and Africa):** Since the project's onset, how often did you perceive that your inputs were not adequately incorporated or valued because of your geographical location?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3) Frequently

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4) Very frequently

l. For team leaders only: how many early career researchers work on the project's activities in your team (early career researchers should have no more than three years postdoctoral experience)

1) 1) 0

2) one or two

3) three or more

m. For team leaders only. Since the project's onset, how frequently did the project offer training/networking opportunities for early career researchers

1) Not at all

2) Sometimes

3) Frequently

4) Very frequently

n. **For early career researchers only:** Since the project's outputs, how frequently did you perceive that being part of the gEneSys project has offered you training/networking opportunities?

1) Not at all

2) Sometimes

3) Frequently

4) Very frequently

o. **For team leaders only:** Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that the resources provided for the project (e.g., budget, time, guidance) were sufficient to effectively deliver the assigned activities?

1) Not at all

2) Sometimes

3) Frequently

4) Very frequently

p. **For team leaders only:** Since the project's onset, how frequently did you perceive that your team has taken advantage of the gEneSys project to create ties with external stakeholders?

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- 1) Not at all
- 2) Sometimes
- 3) Frequently
- 4) Very frequently

q. **For team leaders only:** Since the project's onset, how many opportunities to disseminate project's activities and/or outputs to external stakeholders did you have (e.g., presentation in conferences, running workshops/trainings)

- 1) 1) 0
- 2) one or two
- 3) three or more

r. **For team leaders only** Since the project's onset, to what extent have the project's key themes (e.g. just transition, gendered impacts of energy transition etc.) been mainstreamed into the research of your organisation, beyond the genesys project?

- 1) Not at all
- 2) To a limited extent
- 3) To some extent
- 4) To a great extent

s. Please use this space for any comments on the aspects touched above

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